

Aerodynamic interactions of non-planar rotor pairs and model derivation in ground approach

Ambar Garofano-Soldado^{a,*}, Guillermo Heredia^a, Anibal Ollero^a

^aGRVC Robotics Lab Seville, University of Seville

Abstract

The present work is aimed at analyzing and modeling the aerodynamic interactions of two small-scale tilted propellers operating at low Reynolds numbers near the ground. Two configurations of counter-rotating propellers found in fully-actuated multirotors are investigated: Face-to-Face, where the propeller flows are opposite and non-overlapping, and Back-to-Back, where the interaction between the rotor wakes occurs downstream. Moreover, an aerodynamic ground effect model is proposed for each non-planar rotor pair. To this end, CFD and test-bench experiments are used with different propellers and aerial platforms. Good agreement is found between the output of the proposed models and the numerical-experimental data. We demonstrated that the ground effect depends on rotor spacing, tilt angle, propeller radius, and rotor height, extending previous theories that do not consider these parameters. The results reveal that the near-ground aerodynamic effect for Face-to-Face propellers decreases with increasing inclination, but the opposite behavior is observed for Back-to-Back propellers. Aerial robotics applications require a deep understanding of the effects of multirotors proximity to the environment to reliably and safely perform inspection and maintenance tasks in confined spaces or near infrastructure.

Keywords: Rotor interaction, CFD, tilted rotors, aerial robot, ground effect

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, multirotor UAVs have attracted increasing interest in the scientific community for their ability to carry out tasks that pose a potential risk to humans [1, 2]. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) applications, particularly aerial robotic manipulation tasks or infrastructure inspection, require operation in contact with objects. The focus has been on inspection in the oil and gas industry [3], inspection and maintenance of infrastructure such as bridges [4, 5], viaducts, tunnels [6] or the performance of aerial manipulation tasks [7], [8]. Working conditions in these environments are challenging as they often involve operations at high altitudes in confined scenarios and near surfaces. The aerial platform physically interacts with the environment, resulting in disturbances that require appropriate management.

Multirotor configurations with co-planar propellers are the most popular in a wide range of applications [9]. However, tilt-propeller air vehicles are becoming increasingly common to perform tasks requiring direct contact with infrastructure or flying close to surfaces [10–13]. These UAV configurations do not need to roll or pitch for translational movement. The tilting of the rotor allows thrust to be generated in any direction, enabling horizontal flight. For tasks demanding high precision, safer operations, and more stable flights are achieved. In this regard, several aerial platform designs with non-planar propellers have been proposed in the past literature [14]. The key feature is that it removes the under-actuation constraint of conventional multirotors, where independent control of the UAV's position and orientation is unavailable. This enabled the UAVs to be endowed with 6DoF, making them fully actuated. Unlike co-planar platforms, there are multiple ways to orient and position the rotors to achieve full actuation. The application for which the UAV is to be used will determine the optimum rotor configuration [14]. For contact-based inspection and maintenance, or tasks that require flying close to surfaces, a UAV such as the one in Fig. 1 is typically chosen. Aerial manipulators and other sensors can be installed on such platforms to fulfil the tasks. Along these lines, other researchers have proposed similar configurations [11, 12, 15, 16]. Rotors are usually rotated around their radial axis, known as the cant angle (α). Other work includes the dihedral angle (β), which refers to the rotor rotation relative to the center of the UAV. Although there are different ways of positioning the rotors, S. Rajappa et al. [17] presented the possible configurations to minimize

*Corresponding author: agarofano@us.es

Figure 1: Schematic of the two configurations found on a fully-actuated aerial platform with tilted rotors: Face-to-Face (F-F) where the flows are opposite (left-hand side) and Back-to-Back (B-B) with the flows confronting each other (right-hand side).

the control effort. Two different pairs of non-planar rotors are identified in each feasible variant: Face-to-Face (F-F), where the rotor flows do not intersect, only the blade tip vortices, and Back-to-Back (B-B), where the propeller flows overlap each other [18] (see Fig. 1). These approaches were later adopted by other authors [15, 16, 19–24]. Also, in [15], the feasibility of these configurations was demonstrated by real outdoor flights for a bridge inspection. It should be noted that adjacent non-planar rotors experience strong aerodynamic interaction with each other, which needs to be analyzed. Understanding how forces change with interaction is crucial to the successful accomplishment of tasks in these environments.

Aerodynamic interference occurs due to the proximity of the aerial robot to the surrounding area. The rotor wake will not be able to develop when it encounters an obstacle or surface [25]. As a result, the performance of the rotor varies and needs to be monitored to prevent destabilization of the platform and ensure tasks are completed safely and efficiently. Different aerodynamic interactions occur when a UAV operates nearby surfaces such as the ground [26], ceiling [4, 27–32], wall or corner [33–37]. In particular, the ground effect has been the subject of much research in the past [25, 26] as it causes a significant increase in rotor thrust that is more noticeable at distances closer to the ground. A good comprehension of this phenomenon would make it possible to reduce the rotor thrust in proximity to a surface and fly at lower power. In some scenarios, this effect can be exploited to increase flight time [38]. Much work has been devoted to analyzing the flow behavior of large-scale rotors. However, the propellers typically used in UAVs are small-scale and operate under low Reynolds numbers [39], where flight is difficult due to the high viscous forces [38]. Completing a mission over a long period or with a high payload is an energy constraint beneath these conditions. Optimal path planning or minimization of control efforts would help reduce energy consumption [12, 17]. In this context, some authors have considered the aerodynamic effects in the control stage [4][29][40][32, 41]. These studies focused on the development of new controllers capable of dealing with the different aerodynamic effects. A prior characterization of these effects is necessary to incorporate the models developed into control laws in order to exploit or counteract proximity effects. The result is controllers that can absorb aerodynamic perturbations. However, no aerodynamic models have yet been presented that take into account the interaction of fully-actuated robots with the environment. This requires a thorough understanding of the proximity effects experienced by an air vehicle with tilted propellers. Accordingly, this paper aims to evaluate the aerodynamic interaction of the two pairs of non-planar rotors typically found on fully-actuated vehicles operating near the ground.

Extensive previous research has addressed the ground effect of rotors parallel to the ground. Initial studies were carried out on helicopters, then on small rotors or multirotor UAVs with co-planar configurations under a variety of conditions [42–46]. While many models have been proposed to explain thrust augmentation, the most widely used is Cheeseman and Bennett’s theory [47], which treats the helicopter rotor as a potential source. Additionally, blade element theory (BEM) and the method of images are applied to derive the thrust ratio experienced by a rotor close to the ground. Refer to [25, 26] for a detailed description of the background of co-planar rotors operating near parallel surfaces. In contrast, considering the novel concept of multirotors with tilted propellers, few works have focused on analyzing the influence of rotor inclination at ground level. There is a demand for in-depth and detailed knowledge of how a UAV will behave when performing specific tasks that require UAV-surface interaction. Motivated by the growing use of fully-actuated aerial platforms, the analysis of aerodynamic interactions with tilted rotors is becoming increasingly necessary.

Similarly to conventional platforms, the ground effect considering the inclination, was examined for the first time in helicopters. Fradenburg [48] conducted an experimental analysis of the ground effect, varying the ground inclination and the height of the helicopter rotor. In [49], a tilt-rotor aircraft was tested in the wind tunnel to determine the performance of the rotor and the interaction of the rotor wake with the wing and the stabilizer. Subsequently, an inflow model for inclined ground surfaces was given in [50]. In addition, they identified an asymmetric flow pattern resulting from the inclination of the ground plane. Other recent works [51–53] are based on examining rotor downwash in the vicinity of inclined ground experimentally and by numerical simulation for large-scale propellers. Nevertheless, there

are a limited number of studies on ground effect in the framework of small tilt-rotor UAVs at low Reynolds numbers. Davis et al. [54] explored the lateral position stability of a quadcopter with tilted rotors near a non-planar surface. They found the optimal tilt without compromising stabilization time and overshoot in passive position control. Britcher et al. [34] proposed a model that considered the pressure changes of a small quad-rotor at ground proximity. It also evaluated the inclination of the whole quad-rotor. Afterward, in [55] evaluated the aerodynamic ground effect of a single small-scale tilted rotor. It was found that the ground effect decreases with increasing rotor tilt. An extensive numerical-experimental analysis takes place to understand the physical behavior of the fluid and to model the ground effect for different inclinations and ground distances. However, the model proposed in [55] does not include the possible interaction between adjacent rotors. Mainly its applicability is focused quad-tilt rotor UAVs or VTOL tilt-rotor UAVs, where the rotors are sufficiently separated and flow interactions between different propellers are negligible.

Some authors have shown that the closeness of two rotors creates a blade-tip vortex which causes the flow recirculation and re-ingested into the rotors. As a result, the performance of the entire UAV changes. Therefore, the proximity effect between the rotors must be taken into account in both co-planar [56] and inclined configurations [18]. Li et al. [18] presented the first aerodynamic analysis of two pairs of adjacent non-planar rotors of a fully-actuated multirotor (Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back) in a free environment. Measurements of thrust and torque were collected through wind tunnel tests with wind disturbance for different tilt angles. This research only tested the cant angle. They concluded that the aerodynamic interaction would affect the performance of the complete UAV. However, there are no previous studies that quantify the thrust increment of each of the non-planar rotor pairs of a fully-actuated multirotor in confined environments. As a result, aerodynamic ground effect models do not exist for these rotor pairs, which can be very valuable when only a portion of the UAV is under the influence of a parallel surface, the so-called "partial ground effect" [43]. It will also be useful for some UAV configurations, such as H-shaped quad-copters, where the propellers are paired. For the sake of filling this gap in the literature, this paper assesses and models both the cant angle and the dihedral angle at ground level for Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back pairs.

Generally, aerodynamic interactions can be examined experimentally by bench or wind tunnel tests or by computational fluid dynamics simulations. Ongoing advances in CFD have led to a better understanding of the physical behavior of flow in a wide range of applications. The ability to visualize the flow field is an advantage over bench experimentation. Several methods are available to simulate the flow around a propeller, but the steady-state Multiple-Reference-Frame (MRF) method remains common because of its simplicity and low computational cost. Although several authors have shown its suitability for small and large-scale rotors in narrow and free-standing scenarios [55, 57–61], its applicability to the proposed problem requires verification.

In summary, the main contributions of this research are as follows:

- Investigation of the thrust increase experienced by a two-rotor tilted system in ground proximity using a numerical-experimental evaluation. A wide range of cant (α) and dihedral (β) angles are considered for the Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back rotor pairs. Propeller spacing (d) and various rotor heights z are included. Due to this novel concept of a fully-actuated UAV, no previous analysis or theories have attempted to test the ground effect by varying these parameters (α, β, z, d, R).
- Assessment of the proposed CFD methodology and the reliability of the MRF method in both the Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back cases. The CFD results are compared with experimental data from various test benches. Thus, the scope of the simulation method and the comprehension of the physics of the fluid will be revealed.
- First ground effect models for Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back pairs are presented. Cheeseman and Bennet's theory is extended to derive a new formulation in both cases. Furthermore, the considerations of the single-tilted rotor model [55] are used to incorporate tilt into the proposed ground effect models.

An overview of the rest of the paper is arranged as outlined. Section II presents the experimental set-up, detailing the geometry of the propellers used and the test-bench designed both to achieve the ground effect results and to validate the proposed models. In Section III, the CFD methodology is described. Moreover, the CFD propeller performance is compared with experimental and manufacturer's data to confirm the CFD approach prior to the beginning of the study. Experimental and simulation results for rotors positioned Face-to-Face (F-F) and Back-to-Back (B-B) are reported in Section IV. In Section V, two models of aerodynamic ground effect are presented. The Cheeseman and Bennett theory is modified and extended to include the inclination and separations of the rotors. Section VI is devoted to verifying the proposed models in previous sections with other propellers and aerial platform. Lastly, Section VII summarises the conclusions and discusses future work on aerodynamic interactions in newly emerging fully-actuated aerial platforms.

120 **2. Experimental approach**

2.1. Propeller geometry

The numerical-experimental analysis was performed with different 3D propeller geometries. First, two T-Motor propellers with a pitch of 4.4 inches and a diameter of 13 inches, made from carbon fiber, were used to characterize the ground effect. Second, two DJI plastic propellers with a pitch of 5 inches and a diameter of 9.4 inches were selected to validate the proposed models. The geometrical characteristics are given on the left-hand side of Figs. 2(a)-2(b). Moreover, the chord and pitch distribution of the CAD designs is plotted on the right-hand side of Figs. 2(a)-2(b). These small propellers operate at low Reynolds numbers, defined at 3/4 of the radius location [59, 62]: $Re_{75\%} = \rho V_\omega c_{75\%} / \mu$, where V_ω is the rotational velocity and is given by $V_\omega = \Omega R_{75\%}$, $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the air density, $\mu = 1.7894 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ kg/ms}$ is the dynamic viscosity. $R_{75\%}$ and $c_{75\%}$ is the radius and chord of the propeller at 3/4 of center of hub and Ω is the angular velocity. In this work, the T-Motor propeller works under a Reynolds number of $1.1 \cdot 10^5$ and the DJI propeller $0.58 \cdot 10^5$. Although the propeller performance changes with Re [39], it has been proven in [55] that the ground effect does not depend on the Reynolds number when it is between $(0.46 - 2.2) \cdot 10^5$. For this reason, other Re are not part of this analysis.

Figure 2: Geometric characteristics of the propellers used in this study. The original geometries, 3D CAD designs, and chord and pitch distributions for every propeller are provided. On the one hand, a) shows the T-Motor propeller used to investigate the ground effect of a pair of inclined rotors. On the other hand, b) illustrates the DJI propeller selected to validate the proposed ground effect models.

2.2. Test-bench

135 Fig. 3 shows the test-bench setup to analyze the aerodynamic interaction of non-planar rotor pairs with the ground. It is a $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ aluminum structure with a prototype mounted. The prototype consists of two carbon fiber tubes, a frame, and several inclined pieces, where two motors (T-Motor MN4012) and two propellers are mounted. The body frame and tilted parts are manufactured in PLA (polylactic acid) by 3D printing. Each motor requires three plastic parts and will be swapped according to the α, β configuration chosen. The force/torque Axia80 sensor is placed at the center of the body frame and allows the total forces of the motors-frame assembly to measure under IGE (In-Ground-Effect) and OGE (Out-Ground-Effect) conditions. Three 360W power supplies power the motors and sensor.

145 The motors are controlled by an Arduino Mega, which sends a PWM signal to the motor-propeller system to achieve a specific angular velocity (Ω). During the experiments, a tachometer is used to measure Ω . This results in a speed of 6300 rpm , typically within the operating range of a UAV (50% – 60% throttle). The test procedure is the same as described in [55], where each test lasts 85 seconds. A similar test bench is developed to validate the proposed models in

Figure 3: A test-bench designed to investigate the ground effect of the two pairs of tilted rotors on a fully-actuated aerial vehicle (F-F and B-B). The centre of the prototype is aligned with the force sensor. The aluminium structure is moved perpendicular to the wall in order to position the centre of rotation of the rotors at different z -heights.

Figure 4: Test-stand designed to validate the models described in Sections 5.1 and 5.2 for the Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back cases. The aim is to confirm that the proposed models are valid for propellers of different sizes and materials. The commercial DJI F550 platform is used and only the pair to be studied is activated. New plastic parts are required for each α, β set-up. Similarly, the structure will be moved at different distances from the wall (z).

Table 1: Operating conditions tested in the experimental study and in the validation tests of the proposed models in Sections 4.1 and 4.2.

Parameters	Face to Face (F-F)	Back to Back (B-B)	Validation F-F, B-B
Propeller	T-Motor 13x4.4	T-Motor 13x4.4	DJI 9.4x5
Rotational speed [rpm]	6300	6300	550
α [deg]	$0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ$	$0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ$	$10^\circ, 20^\circ$
β [deg]	0°	$0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ$	$10^\circ, 20^\circ$
Nondimensional ground distance (z/R)	0.6, 0.75, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 5	0.6, 0.75, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 5	1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, 5

Sections 4.1 and 4.2 for the F-F and B-B configuration with other propellers (see Fig. 4). Accordingly, a commercial DJI platform was installed, with plastic parts similar to those suggested by [15]. It uses two DJI 9.4x5 propellers and two DJI E310 2312 CCW/CW motors.

The parameters modified to analyze the ground effect are the dimensionless distance z/R , the angles α , and β . Table 1 gives a summary of the operating conditions. Furthermore, Fig. 5 illustrates the adopted sign criterion of α , β according to [17]. Feasible configurations to minimize the control effort for a given trajectory, and thus minimize the energy consumption are presented in [17]. Among the different alternatives, the best combinations of α - β in a fully-actuated hexarotor are shown on the left-hand side of Figs. 6(a)-6(b). In both cases, the direction of rotation of the α and β angles alternate between adjacent rotors, giving rise to the two pairs of rotors analyzed in this work: Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back. On the one hand, in Fig. 6(a), the α and β angles have the same sign for a motor,

Figure 5: Sign criterion considered according to [17]. Angle α is the rotation relative to the X-axis (a) and angle β is the rotation related to the Y-axis (b). Depending on the angle at which it is turned, the plastic part will change its inclination and with it the position of the propeller.

Table 2: Operating conditions examined in the numerical study and in the CFD validation of the proposed models in Sections 5.1 and 5.2.

Parameters	Face to Face (F-F)	Back to Back (B-B)	Validation F-F
Propeller	T-Motor 13x4.4	T-Motor 13x4.4	DJI 9.4x5
Rotational speed [rpm]	6300	6300	5500
α [deg]	$10^\circ, 20^\circ$	$10^\circ, 20^\circ$	$10^\circ, 20^\circ$
β [deg]	$0^\circ, 10^\circ$	0°	10°
Nondimensional ground distance (z/R)	0.75, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 3, 4, 5	0.75, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 3, 4, 5	1, 1.5, 2.5, 3, 4, 5

Figure 6: Optimal α - β configurations to minimize control effort for a given trajectory following [17]. On the left is the direction of rotation of each angle (α, β) for a hexarotor. The circles represent the individual rotors and α_i - β_i are related to the angle of each propeller (i -th). In the middle and on the right, the pairs Face-to-Face (F-F) and Back-to-Back (B-B) are shown, depending on whether $\alpha_i = \beta_i$ (a) or $\alpha_i = -\beta_i$ (b).

while in Fig. 6(b), have an opposite direction of rotation in each motor. Nevertheless, the interaction between the flows is the same in both configurations, as can be seen on the right and in the middle of Figs. 6(a) -6(b).

In total, 158 experiments have been carried out: 36 to study the Face-to-Face (F-F) configuration, 108 to analyze the Back-to-Back (B-B) pair, and 14 to validate the proposed models with a propeller of different material and size. Five tests are carried out in each experiment to obtain the average force for each z/R , α , and β . Experimental results will be presented in Section 4, and can be found on our GitHub page [63].

Figure 7: Scheme of the computational domains generated in the numerical study (see (a)). There are two rotational domains with a propeller in their interior and a stationary domain consisting of an inner and an outer domain (ID, OD). The geometrical parameters of these domains are given, as well as the boundary conditions involved. Also, the geometrical design for the F-F and B-B configurations is provided (see (b) and (c)).

3. Numerical approach

This section describes the procedure for performing CFD simulations. It provides a detailed discussion of geometry, meshing, boundary conditions, and numerical methods. Note that all simulations were conducted using the commercial software ANSYS-Fluent.

3.1. CFD methodology

Regarding CFD methods for modelling the 3D flow around a propeller, there are the Multiple Reference Frame model or the sliding mesh model [59, 60, 64, 65]. These techniques make it possible to separate the zones in motion (rotating domain) from those containing stationary surfaces (stationary domain). On the one hand, the sliding mesh model considers the relative movement of the rotational domain concerning the adjacent zones. As a result, the mesh changes at each time step, resulting in a time-dependent solution. On the other hand, MRF is based on steady-state flow modelling where the mesh remains fixed throughout the calculation [66]. Also, it measures the instantaneous fluid flow at a given position. Although the MRF method does not support the modeling of transient effects, ANSYS-FLUENT allows you to include unsteady terms [66]. The present work uses the MRF method because of its relatively low computational cost and faster solution time. Furthermore, as demonstrated in previous work [55, 57, 64], it is possible to accurately model the ground effect for both co-planar and inclined rotors. However, it is necessary to verify that MRF behaves correctly with a pair of propellers whose flows interact under IGE/OGE conditions.

Figure 8: Full computational domain mesh. Detail of prototype mesh consisting of the frame (central disc and two arms), two propellers, and the rotational domains. The inner domain (ID) has a finer mesh to achieve the transition between the propeller and the ground, allowing a higher precision in the rotor wake.

Fig. 7(a) illustrates the complete computational domain generated and Figs. 7(b)- 7(c) show the details of the created geometries for the Face to Face and Back to Back cases, respectively. First, the stationary domain consists of an outer domain (OD) and an inner domain (ID) that models the rotor wake. To capture the flow more accurately, ID allows refinement of the mesh near the ground. In addition, a body frame consisting of a circular base and two cylindrical tubes is fixed within the stationary domain. Next, create two rotation domains, one for each propeller. For

Figure 9: Propeller mesh included in this study. Firstly, the T-Motor propeller is used for MRF evaluation in the F-F and B-B pairs and, where possible, for flow field visualization. Secondly, the DJI propeller is utilized to validate the proposed ground effect models.

Table 3: Mesh element size of the various components that make up the geometry of the two DJI propellers and the UAV body.

Surfaces	Element size (mm)
Propeller	0.8
Edge blade	0.3
Tip blade	0.2
Body frame	0.2
Interfaces	5

the sake of simplicity, the plastic parts and motors, shown in Fig. 3, are not included in the numerical analysis. Fig. 7 details the dimensions of each domain and the boundary conditions. The geometry of the two propellers and the UAV body frame is tailored to the measurements of the actual scenario (see Fig. 3). As pointed out by C. Paz et al. [64], the position of the propeller relative to the body frame plays an important role in the MRF method. Consequently, and according to [64], the propellers are placed perpendicular to the UAV arm (see Fig. 7).

Next, the no-slip wall condition applies to each propeller, the body frame, and the ground plane. Pressure inlet and pressure outlet conditions are set in the top and lateral boundary of the outer domain, respectively. Lastly, it is necessary to create an interface between each rotational and stationary area that enables the exchange of information between the two zones. The same angular velocity applies to the two propellers but in opposite directions to each other. Table 2 gives the operating conditions taken into account in the numerical analysis. A total of 58 CFD simulations have been performed: 16 for the F-F configuration, 14 for the B-B case, 14 for the validation of the proposed model for non-zero β and 14 for the validation process with another propeller. On the one hand, the F-F and B-B configurations are investigated and compared with the experimental results when $\beta = 0^\circ$. The aim is to determine whether MRF is sufficient to reproduce the flow characteristics and correctly identify the ground effect with inclined rotor pairs. On the other hand, MRF will be used to validate the proposed F-F model for $\beta \neq 0^\circ$ cases and for additional propellers. If the MRF is inappropriate for evaluating a configuration, then bench testing is required.

3.2. Meshing

All simulations consider unstructured meshes. In the first part of the numerical analysis, the mesh characteristics are similar to those proposed in [55] for the T-Motor propeller, where a mesh independence study has been performed to obtain a cost-accuracy trade-off solution. Furthermore, the element size of the body frame is defined as $0.002m$ in this analysis. Next, for the simulations conducted with the DJI 9.4x5 propeller, the size of the elements is given in Table 3. Fig. 8 depicts the mesh of the entire computational domain. In addition, Figs. 9(a) - 9(b) illustrate the mesh of the T-Motor and DJI propeller, respectively. The mesh quality parameters have been checked to ensure accurate results. In particular, it was verified that the orthogonal quality does not exceed 0.15 [60].

Regarding the calculation process, the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations are solved considering incompressible flow. In view of the low Reynolds number range, the shear-stress transport (SST) $k-\omega$ turbulence model is chosen [67]. The SST model is already widely used by other authors [59], [60], [68], and the reliability in identifying the ground effect was studied in previous work [55]. The coupled pressure-based algorithm is applied. The spatial discretisation uses PRESTO for the pressure interpolation scheme, the power law scheme for the momentum equation and a first-order scheme for turbulent kinetic energy (k) and specific dissipation (ω). Higher-order schemes make the convergence of the solution more difficult.

3.3. Propeller performance

Before examining the ground effect in a two-rotor system, the proposed CFD methodology is verified to predict the static performance of the propeller in a free environment. For this purpose, a total of 14 new simulations are performed. The CFD results of the T-Motor propeller are compared with manufacturer's data [69] and DJI's with experimental data, as no manufacturer's data is available.

Figs. 10(a)- 10(b) show the evolution of the thrust (T) and torque (Q) with different angular velocities (Ω) for the T-Motor and DJI propeller, respectively. The CFD curves were obtained by interpolation. On the one hand, for the

Figure 10: Evolution of thrust and torque with angular velocity (Ω). First in *a*), for the T-Motor propeller, the CFD results are matched with the manufacturer's data. Then in *b*), for the DJI propeller, the CFD results are compared with those obtained experimentally.

Figure 11: Thrust ratio versus dimensionless distance z/R for the pair of rotors in Face-to-Face configuration. On the one hand, (a) shows the experimental results for various angles α and $\beta = 0^\circ$. On the other hand, in (b), the experimental measurements are compared with the CFD results achieved after applying the MRF method. It is considered that $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$.

T-Motor propeller, the numerical results are in good agreement with the manufacturer's data. On the other hand, for the DJI propeller, the thrust obtained from CFD underestimates the experimental results, while the opposite is true for the torque. Also, the error increases with angular velocity. In any case, the maximum errors of thrust and torque do not exceed 6% and 10%, respectively. Thus, the CFD methodology is adequate to reproduce the propeller performance and will be applied to explore ground effects in non-planar rotor pairs.

4. Proximity effects in a non-planar two-rotor system

This section presents the aerodynamic interactions between two tilted rotors in the Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back configurations close to the ground. Experiments for different inclinations are presented and compared with the CFD results. First, only the angle α is varied to see the contribution of a unique angle. Subsequently, the angle β is included to investigate the dual inclination ground effect.

4.1. Evaluation and flow field visualization in the F-F pair

Ground effect is usually expressed in terms of the thrust ratio T_{IGE}/T_{OGE} , where T_{IGE} (In-Ground-Effect) is the rotor thrust when influenced by the proximity of the ground and T_{OGE} (Out-of-Ground-Effect) is the rotor thrust when the ground effect is negligible. The rotor performance is affected by the presence of the ground, which causes a reduction in the averaged induced velocity [52, 70]. Furthermore, from an engineering point of view, the ground effect increases thrust at constant power. In this analysis, T_{IGE} and T_{OGE} are the total thrust of the UAV, considering both the thrust of the rotors and the contribution of the body frame under IGE and OGE conditions, respectively. In addition, the angles α, β and the dimensionless height z/R are considered.

(a) Flow field for $\alpha = 10^\circ$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$

(b) Flow field for $\alpha = 20^\circ$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$

Figure 12: Velocity contour and velocity vectors in the plane of the propellers for angles $\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$ on the left side. Streamlines are drawn on the middle and right sides in order to visualize the ground vortices and blade tip vortices resulting from the interaction between the two propellers. All figures correspond to the height $z = 1R$, measured from the rotational center of the rotor to the ground.

Figure 13: Velocity contours plotted at different cross-sections parallel to the ground under the propellers ($z = R/7, R/2, 3R/4$). In addition, the contours are compared for angles $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$.

On the one hand, Fig. 11(a) shows the experimental ground effect results for a pair of Face-to-Face rotors with angles $\alpha = 0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ$. Ten rotor heights are considered, not including values above $z = 5R$, as the thrust ratio remains constant. It is noticeable that the ground effect decreases as the angle of inclination (α) increases. Similarly, from $z = 3R$ onwards, the thrust increase is negligible for all cases. On the other hand, Fig. 11(b) illustrates the thrust ratio obtained from CFD simulations for the inclinations 10° and 20° . There is also a comparison of numerical results with experimental data. The maximum error found is 4.5%, while for most heights, the error does not reach 1%. The observed discrepancies are due to errors introduced by the experimental and simulation processes. Nevertheless, the errors are low and can therefore be accepted. Accordingly, the CFD methodology presented in Section 3 is suitable for predicting the flow characteristics in the vicinity of the ground for a pair of F-F rotors. The numerical analysis makes it possible to visualize the flow field and understand the thrust generation mechanisms

The presence of the ground restricts the rotor downwash flow, resulting in a radial flow expansion. The interaction of the flow with the ground produces the creation of two flow structures (ground vortices) in the central region of the propeller, as can be seen in Figs. 12(a)- 12(b). Furthermore, two sub-structures appear under the propeller close to the central hub. The height $z = 1R$ is used in all figures. On the left is the velocity contour, along with the velocity

Figure 14: Vorticity contours depicted at different cross-sections parallel to the ground under the propellers ($z = R/7, R/2, 3R/4$). The contours are compared for angles $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$.

Figure 15: Evolution of the thrust ratio with distance from the ground in the F-F pair. The experimental data are compared with the single-tilted rotor model [55].

255 vectors. It gives an idea of the evolution of velocities and the direction of the airflow. It also shows how the blade tip vortices of the two propellers interact by observing the intersection of the two planes. On the right-hand side and in the middle, the streamlines are plotted for propeller 1 (P1), and propeller 2 (P2), respectively. The flow pattern is similar to the one presented in [55], where the size of the vortices decreases with angle as the flow can expand faster. Also, note that the velocities are higher on the upward side (at the end of the propeller furthest from the ground). It causes an increasingly asymmetric flow pattern. In contrast to previous work, a vortex appears on the downward side (end of the propeller closest to the ground) due to the interaction between the flows of propellers 1 and 2. As the rotor tilt
 260 increases, the downward side of the propeller is closer to the ground, reducing the size of the blade tip vortices.

265 Fig. 13 draws the velocity contour of three cross-sections parallel to the ground. The propellers are at a distance of $1R$ from the ground. Contrary to the results for a coplanar multirotor UAV [64], the inclination causes a displacement of the velocity contour and will be stronger at higher angles. In the areas closest to the ground ($z = 3R/4$), flow expands radially. In addition, it also reveals an asymmetric flow pattern as the X-Y plane approaches the ground. The interaction between propellers and the UAV body is also visualized. To complement this study, Fig. 14 depicts the vorticity contours in the X-Y plane. In the cross-section closest to the propeller ($z = R/7$), the region where the two flows interact is evident (downward side of the propeller). The two sub-structures shown in Figs. 12(a)- 12(b) are also found in the propeller mid-zone. The vorticity is reduced at higher angles because the vortices become smaller. As can be seen at height $z = 3R/4$, there is an increase in vorticity as the flow reaches the ground and spreads radially.
 270 Moreover, the ground vortices in the propeller mid-zone are visible for $\alpha = 10^\circ$ due to their larger size than for $\alpha = 20^\circ$.

Additionally, Fig. 15 contrasts the experimental results with the ground effect model of a tilted rotor (θ) [55]. The

Figure 16: Diagram to get the angle between the propeller plane (π_i) and the ground plane (π_j). Knowing the normal to the propeller plane (\vec{n}_i) and the normal to the ground (\vec{n}_j), the angle θ is determined.

observed trend is similar to a single-tilted rotor, where the propeller inclination is related to the angle between the propeller plane and the ground, θ (see Fig. 16). However, Fig. 15 illustrates the gap between the distances $0.6R$ and $1.3R$. The error decreases as the angle α increases because both the blade tip vortices and the two flow structures are smaller. In such cases, the interaction between propellers is less as the flow spreads more easily (see Figs. 12(a)-12(b)), making the single-tilted rotor model more relevant. This suggests that the proximity effect between adjacent propellers close to the ground is relevant.

As in [55], the angle θ is determined as a combination of the angles involved. For that, it is necessary to consider the normal to the ground plane ($\vec{n}_j = [0 \ 0 \ 1]$) and to define the normal to the propeller plane (\vec{n}_i). For this purpose, a rotation is applied to each coordinate axis: the α rotation is made to the X-axis and the β rotation is relative to the Y-axis. Here it is possible to rotate α first and then β , or the other way around. In both cases, the angle of the propeller plane to the ground is always the same. Therefore, leaving either α or β fixed and increasing the other angle will result in an increase in θ . In [55] it was demonstrated that the ground effect decreases with increasing θ . In the Face-to-Face pair, it is assumed that the angle θ can be obtained as a combination of α , β since the trend seen in Fig. 15 is very similar to that of the single-tilted rotor. This hypothesis will be proven in Section 5.1. In contrast, in the Back-to-Back pair, the angle θ is not used because the strong interaction between the flows reverses the ground effect trend (see Section 4.2), and angles α , β must be considered individually.

The different results described above are consistent with the ground effect trend found in Fig. 11(a). The propeller interaction and the ground vortices are in line with those reported in [52, 55, 64]. The MRF approach correctly detects shape and size changes in the vortices. Thus, the F-F configuration can use numerical simulations to evaluate the variation of angle β in ground proximity.

Figure 17: Thrust ratio against dimensionless z/R for two Back-to-Back positioned rotors. On the one hand, (a) shows the experimental results for different angles α and $\beta = 0^\circ$. On the other hand, (b) illustrates the comparison between experimental and simulation data. The cases analyzed are the same as for the F-F pair.

4.2. Analysis of the B-B pair

Fig. 17(a) shows the thrust ratio experienced by the prototype with the Back-to-Back pair for ten heights and various angles $\alpha = 0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ$, $\beta = 0^\circ$ (see Table 1). Between $0.6R$ and $1R$, a similar trend to the Face-to-Face configuration and the isolated inclined rotor [55] can be seen. However, from $z = 1R$ onwards, an increase in the ground effect is observed concerning Fig. 11(a). When $z = 1.5R$, there are no significant differences between the co-planar and inclined cases. The flows interact with each other and the ground, generating a more complex behavior than previously

analyzed. It suggests that if the β is included, the ground effect may be different from that shown in the Face-to-Face configuration.

Figure 18: Evolution of the ground effect taking into account the inclinations with respect to the Y-axis and X-axis (β and α) in the Back-to-Back configuration. The data were obtained experimentally with the test-bed shown in Fig. 3 for ten different heights (z). Rising trend with angle β shows a contrasting behavior to previous works.

Next, the B-B pair is subject to the MRF method evaluation. Fig. 17(b) compares the CFD results and experimental data. The selected cases are the same as those presented in the F-F pair ($\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$). Note how the simulation data does not capture the downward trend with angle α or the expected increase in thrust ratio from $1R$. Accordingly, in the Back-to-Back case, the evolution of the ground effect with angle is not predictable, and the proposed CFD methodology is unreliable. There is interference between the flows, and the steady-state MRF method is insufficient to characterize the ground effect in this configuration. Instead, non-stationary techniques need to explore for improvement of the results. However, with the large number of cases to assess to understand the inter-dependencies of this phenomenon, the cost of computing and the time required are unaffordable. Therefore, the Back-to-Back configuration is studied in an extensive campaign of experiments.

Concerning the angle β , its contribution to the ground effect is examined in detail. Fig. 18 plots the experimental results of thrust ratio for different combinations of α , β in the Back-to-Back pair. Each angle α has a different colour, while several markers represent the variation of β . Note that if α is constant and β increases, the thrust ratio will increase. However, the ground effect will be more noticeable at higher cant angles (α). So for $\alpha = 0^\circ$ the thrust ratio remains unchanged, while for higher values of α ($20^\circ, 30^\circ$) there is a 10% leap in thrust ratio between the case of $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 20^\circ$ for distances close to the ground. This shows that the change in α causes the most interference in this pair of rotors. Furthermore, a comparison of Fig. 17(a), where only α varies, with the upper left graph in Fig. 18, where only β varies, reveals that the variation in cant angle has a more significant impact on the ground effect. It is worth noting that the trend in Fig. 18 is opposite to that observed in Fig. 17(a) where, by keeping β fixed and varying α , the ground effect decreased as the cant angle increased. A similar pattern was observed for the Face-to-Face pair or single-tilted rotor.

In general, depending on the angle varied, two clear trends are identified from the experimental results. As a result, the previous models are not applicable as the cant and dihedral angles have to be considered individually.

5. Aerodynamic ground effect model for tilted rotor pairs

This section describes two ground effect models, one for the F-F configuration, and one for the rotor pair placed B-B. It also presents the validation of the proposed models with experimental and simulation results.

5.1. Face-to-Face configuration

Cheeseman and Bennet's classical theory has been widely used to model the ground effect in large and small-scale rotors. It uses the method of images to establish the ground boundary condition and treats the rotor as a potential

Figure 19: Schematic to illustrate assumptions 1 and 3 made in Section 5.1. Each rotor is considered as a source, separated by a distance d . In the intermediate zone between the two propellers ($d/2$) the greatest interference occurs.

Figure 20: Thrust increase obtained by the proposed model of the F-F rotor pair compared with experimental data in a), and CFD data in b).

source. These assumptions lead to $T_{IGE}/T_{OGE} = \frac{1}{1 - \delta v_i(z)/v_{i\infty}}$, being δv_i the velocity induced in the rotor by the image placed at a distance z and defined as follows: $\delta v_i(z) = \frac{Av_{i\infty}}{16\pi z^2}$. The source strength is $Av_{i\infty}/4\pi$, where A is the rotor disk area ($A = \pi R^2$). Under these considerations, the classical theory is modified in [55] to include the tilt angle (θ). Because of the CFD results and considering the approximations of the inflow models for different flight conditions [71], the induced velocity was approximated by the first harmonic of a trigonometric function: $v_{OGE} = v_{i\infty} f_c(\theta) = v_{i\infty} \cdot (a_0 + a_1 \sin(\theta) + b_1 \cos(\theta))$, and thus [55]:

$$\delta v_i(z, \theta) = \frac{Av_{i\infty} \cdot (a_0 + a_1 \sin(\theta) + b_1 \cos(\theta))}{16\pi z^2} \quad (1)$$

where $v_{OGE} = v_{i\infty} f_c(\theta)$ is the induced velocity Out-of-Ground-Effect for a single-tilted rotor (STR). The current work proposes a variation of Eq. (1) to include rotor spacing (d), tilt angles, rotor's height (z), and propeller radius (R). Different assumptions are made to derive the aerodynamic model of a pair of F-F rotors:

Assumption 1: each rotor is considered a 3D potential source. The superposition principle of these two sources and the method of images is applied to simulate the ground. The reference system and the variables of interest are specified in Fig. 19. Thus, the ground effect for two rotors would be:

$$\left[\frac{T_{IGE_{F-F}}}{T_{OGE_{F-F}}} \right]_{(z, \theta)} = \frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{\delta v_{i_1}(z, \theta)}{v_{i\infty}} \right) - \left(\frac{\delta v_{i_2}(z, \theta)}{v_{i\infty}} \right)} \quad (2)$$

Assumption 2: the presence of the ground reduces the induced velocity of the rotor [47]. This change causes an increase in the thrust ratio and the occurrence of the ground effect. As shown in previous work [52], [55], as the tilt angle increases, the flow can spread easier, causing the induced velocity to become less and less reduced. Accordingly, the ground effect will gradually decrease with the angle. Fig. 11(a) displays a similar trend as that achieved in [55] after applying Eq. (1). Therefore, the induced velocity approximation in the F-F pair is the same as for a single rotor

Assumption 3: rotor 2 is positioned at $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (d, 0, z)$ relative to the absolute system. However, as can be seen in Figs. 12(a)-12(b), at $d/2$ is the position at which the interaction of the blade tip vortices of both propellers will occur. For this reason, the induced velocity in rotor 2 caused by its image rotor is determined relative to $(d/2, 0, z)$.

Table 4: Definition of dimensionless coefficients involved in the induced velocity model for the single-tilted rotor (STR) and for the rotor pairs F-F and B-B.

Model	K_c	K_j	K_h
STR and F-F pair	a_0	a_1	b_1
B-B pair	c_0	$c_1 \sin(\beta)$	$c_2 \cos(\beta)$

Fig. 19 depicts in shaded black the area belonging to $d/2$.

350 As a result, the aerodynamic ground effect model developed for the pair of non-planar rotors F-F is as follows:

$$\left[\frac{T_{IGE_{F-F}}}{T_{OGE_{F-F}}} \right]_{(z,\theta)} = \frac{1}{1 - \left[\left(\frac{R}{4z} \right)^2 + \frac{R^2}{2} \frac{z}{\left[\left(\frac{d}{2} \right)^2 + 4z^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right]} \cdot f_c(\theta) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 20(a) presents the experimental results for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ$ and compares them with the proposed F-F two-rotor model (Eq. (3)). The Face-to-Face model is in good agreement with the experimental data and fits better than the one-rotor model [55] (see Fig. 15). However, some deviations at distances very close to the ground plane could be due to the measurements taken at these points. In any case, the errors found are less than 5% for the distance $z = 0.6R$ and the inclinations $\alpha = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, \beta = 0^\circ$ and lower than 3% at $z = 0.6R$ and $\alpha = 20^\circ, \beta = 0^\circ$. For all other cases, the errors are less than 2%. Note that if the distance d becomes larger, the two-rotor model (Eq. (1)) gives the same outputs as the one-rotor model (Eq. (3)). In this case, the single-tilted rotor model is recommended due to its simplicity when the rotor spacing is large enough. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the proposed F-F model gives a good approximation to estimate the thrust ratio of a pair of rotors in the F-F configuration in ground proximity.

360 Next, the proposed model is evaluated when $\beta \neq 0^\circ$, since some aerial vehicles have double-tilt rotors [15, 17, 22, 23, 72]. To this end, new numerical simulations, previously validated, are performed. Fig. 20(b) plots the thrust ratio obtained with the CFD results and the outputs of the F-F aerodynamic model for $\alpha = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$ and $\beta = 10^\circ$. The simulation data fit well with the proposed model, which reveals that the fluid behavior was as expected.

365 5.2. Back-to-Back configuration

A new aerodynamic model has to be defined for the Back-to-Back pair, as the thrust ratio trends are contrary to the F-F configuration and single-tilted rotor. Consequently, the induced velocity model of the inclined rotor becomes inapplicable, and the function $f_c(\theta)$ can no longer be used. However, assumptions 1 and 3 of the Face-to-Face rotors remain valid. In general, the induced velocity model proposed in [55] can be expressed as follows:

$$v_{OGE_{STR,FF}} = v_{i\infty} f_c(\theta) = v_{i\infty} (K_c + K_j \cos(\theta) + K_h \sin(\theta)) \quad (4)$$

370 where K_c, K_j, K_h are coefficients to be determined. Historically, several authors have employed the first harmonic for inflow models under different operating conditions (vertical, forward, hovering and low-speed flight) [71]. Its suitability has been demonstrated for small and large scale rotors. In this novel configuration, new coefficients are proposed. Table 4 summarises the value of these coefficients for the different use cases. In particular, for the B-B pair, it is considered that $\theta = \alpha$ in Eq. (4). Also, c_0, c_1 and c_2 are dimensionless coefficients. Therefore, in this case, it is set as:

$$v_{OGE_{BB}} = v_{i\infty} [c_0 + c_1 \cos(\alpha) \sin(\beta) + c_2 \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta)] = v_{i\infty} f_m(\alpha, \beta) \quad (5)$$

375 where $f_m(\alpha, \beta)$ is the objective function. This will make δv_{i_1} and δv_{i_2} a function of α, β and z .

As a result, the ground effect model for two rotors in the Back to Back position will be:

$$\left[\frac{T_{IGE_{B-B}}}{T_{OGE_{B-B}}} \right]_{(z,\alpha,\beta)} = \frac{1}{1 - \left[\left(\frac{R}{4z} \right)^2 + \frac{R^2}{2} \frac{z}{\left[\left(\frac{d}{2} \right)^2 + 4z^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right]} \cdot f_m(\alpha, \beta) \quad (6)$$

Figure 21: Thrust ratio for Back-to-Back positioned rotors: comparison of experimental measurements with output from the proposed model in Eq. (6)- Eq.(7). Representation of the ground effect for differens angles (α, β) and heights (z) .

Using Eq. (6) and the experimental data of Fig. 18, the values of c_0 , c_1 and c_2 are determined. The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm is used to obtain the dimensionless coefficients. This method allows for solving nonlinear least squares problems. Thus, the values achieved are as below:

$$\begin{aligned} c_0 &= 0.591 \\ c_1 &= 0.854 \\ c_2 &= -0.134 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Figs. 21(a)-21(c) depict in dashed lines, the results obtained by applying the proposed model of Eq. (6)-Eq. (7). These are also compared with the experimental data shown in the solid line. A good agreement between both cases is found where the errors are negligible and below 1% for all points.

6. Verification of proposed models with other propellers

The models developed in the previous sections are dimensionless and depend on the UAV settings. It is assumed that the parameters z , d , R , and inclinations (α, β) can be changed and that the models remain valid since the ground effect will follow the same trend. On the one hand, there is evidence that Cheeseman and Bennett's theory applies to rotors of different sizes. On the other hand, in [55], the assumptions made to include inclination in a single rotor were tested on propellers with diameters between 9 and 18 inches, operating at Reynolds numbers in the range $(0.46 - 2.2) \cdot 10^5$. Since this work extends previous theories by considering each rotor as a potential source and by including the inclination in the induced velocity, similar to [55], the scope of the proposed models is expected to be similar. Therefore, the models for a tilted two-rotor system are valid for the same range of applications as the single-tilted rotor model. It is worth noting that it covers a wide variety of cases, as these are the propellers typically used in UAVs to perform different tasks.

In order to validate these considerations, propellers of different sizes, geometry, and material were tested. New CFD simulations and bench tests were conducted (see Tables 1-2). The commercial DJI F550 aerial platform was chosen to analyze the F-F and B-B cases (see Fig. 4). Several arbitrary inclinations are selected for both numerical and experimental studies. On the experiment side, $\alpha = \beta = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$ is used. On the simulation side, $\alpha = \beta = 10^\circ$ is considered to check if there are differences with the experimental data, and $\alpha = 20^\circ, \beta = 10^\circ$ to examine a configuration different from the above. In addition, in all cases it is established that $\beta \neq 0^\circ$ since the case of $\beta = 0^\circ$ was discussed in detail in previous sections. Note that experiments were only carried out for the B-B pair, because, as shown in section 4.2, the MRF method was not adequate to predict the ground effect.

Figs. 22(a)-22(b) compare the test-stand and CFD results with those predicted by the F-F ground effect model, respectively. Good agreement is evident in both figures, where the errors are less than 1%. Likewise, Fig. 22(c) gives the thrust ratio obtained with the B-B model and compares it with the experimental measurements. Looking at Fig. 22(a) and Fig. 22(c) it can be noticed that for the same inclination ($\alpha = \beta = 10^\circ, 20^\circ$), the thrust ratio is significantly higher for B-B, as discussed in previous sections. In general, it is observed that the proposed models fit well with both CFD and experimental data, demonstrating their reliability and accuracy. The errors found are minimal and less than 1% in all scenarios.

Figure 22: Validation of the aerodynamic ground effect model with the DJI propeller. The thrust ratio is plotted against the dimensionless distance z/R_v , where R_v is the radius of the DJI propeller. In (a), the experimental data collected from the test bed (see Fig. 4) are compared with the results of the F-F model. In (b), the CFD data are contrasted with the output of the F-F model. In (c), the experimental data are checked against the outcome of the B-B model.

7. Conclusions and future works

A combined experimental and CFD-based approach is used to investigate the aerodynamic interaction of two pairs of non-planar rotors close to the ground. In particular, Face-to-Face and Back-to-Back configurations were studied. Each pair of rotors in a fully-actuated UAV behaves differently. A lack of information exists on how proximity to the ground affects these configurations as this is an emerging fully-actuated UAV technology. Different inclinations (α, β) and heights (z) with respect to the ground are tested. In the end, we proposed two models of the aerodynamic ground effect, one for each configuration.

The results reported in this analysis illustrate the thrust increase experienced by a two-rotor system and how it varies with inclination. Two opposing behaviors have been identified. On the one hand, the Face-to-Face pair shows a similar trend to the previous model of a single-tilted rotor whether α or β is increased. In this scenario, the ground effect is reduced. However, the interaction of the blade tip vortices of both propellers causes deviations from the single rotor case. Therefore, a new model is needed that includes the rotor spacing (d). On the other hand, the B-B rotors display an opposite behaviour. In this configuration, if α remains constant and β varies, the ground effect becomes higher. The reverse happens when α changes, and β is fixed. As a result, the F-F model is not applicable.

For the development of aerodynamic models in both pairs, different considerations were made based on the extension of Cheeseman and Bennet’s theory. Moreover, in the F-F case, previous formulations are considered to include the tilt. However, the B-B rotors require an experimental driven-data model. The proposed models fit well with experimental results and CFD data for propellers of different sizes and materials.

CFD methods were applied to investigate the two sets of rotors. In particular, the MRF method was used to simulate the propeller flow. However, its applicability is limited to the F-F case only. In the B-B rotors, the interaction is very strong and a steady-state approximation might not be sufficient. The CFD results have made it possible to minimise the number of experiments on the F-F rotors and to visualise the flow field in order to understand the physical behaviour of the fluid.

In future work, the proposed models will be implemented in the control laws to support the stabilisation of the platform. The aim is to achieve safer operations and consumption savings for the UAV. Furthermore, the results suggest that the ground effect on complete aerial platforms with tilted rotors will vary compared to co-planar multirotors. This scenario will be further investigated in the future to give a close solution to this problem.

8. Acknowledgements

This work has been partially supported by the MARTIN project (Grant PID2022-143267OB-I00) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe”, and by the H2020 PILOTING (H2020-ICT-2019-2-871542), and Horizon Europe SIMAR (HORIZON-CL4-2021-101070604) projects, funded by the European Union. The work of Ambar Garofano-Soldado is supported by the FPI grant from the Ministry of Science and Innovation of the Spanish Government.

References

- [1] F. Ruggiero, V. Lippiello, A. Ollero, Aerial manipulation: A literature review, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 3 (3) (2018) 1957–1964. doi:10.1109/LRA.2018.2808541.
- [2] H. Shakhathreh, A. H. Sawalmeh, A. Al-Fuqaha, Z. Dou, E. Almaita, I. Khalil, N. S. Othman, A. Khreishah, M. Guizani, Unmanned aerial vehicles (uavs): A survey on civil applications and key research challenges, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 48572–48634. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2909530.
- [3] A. Ollero, G. Heredia, A. Franchi, G. Antonelli, K. Kondak, A. Sanfeliu, A. Viguria, J. R. Martinez-de Dios, F. Pierri, J. Cortes, A. Santamaria-Navarro, M. A. Trujillo Soto, R. Balachandran, J. Andrade-Cetto, A. Rodriguez, The aeroarms project: Aerial robots with advanced manipulation capabilities for inspection and maintenance, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine* 25 (4) (2018) 12–23. doi:10.1109/MRA.2018.2852789.
- [4] A. E. Jimenez-Cano, P. J. Sanchez-Cuevas, P. Grau, A. Ollero, G. Heredia, Contact-based bridge inspection multi-rotors: Design, modeling, and control considering the ceiling effect, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 4 (4) (2019) 3561–3568. doi:10.1109/LRA.2019.2928206.
- [5] P. J. Sanchez-Cuevas, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Multirotor uas for bridge inspection by contact using the ceiling effect, in: *2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, 2017, pp. 767–774. doi:10.1109/ICUAS.2017.7991412.
- [6] D. Benjumea, A. Alcantara, A. Ramos, A. Torres-Gonzalez, P. Sanchez-Cuevas, J. Capitan, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Localization system for lightweight unmanned aerial vehicles in inspection tasks, *Sensors* 21 (17) (2021). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/17/5937>
- [7] M. Fumagalli, R. Naldi, A. Macchelli, F. Forte, A. Q. Keemink, S. Stramigioli, R. Carloni, L. Marconi, Developing an aerial manipulator prototype: Physical interaction with the environment, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine* 21 (3) (2014) 41–50. doi:10.1109/MRA.2013.2287454.
- [8] A. Ollero, M. Tognon, A. Suarez, D. Lee, A. Franchi, Past, present, and future of aerial robotic manipulators, *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* (2021).
- [9] K. P. Valavanis, G. J. Vachtsevanos, *Handbook of unmanned aerial vehicles*, Vol. 2077, Springer, 2015.
- [10] S. Park, J. Lee, J. Ahn, M. Kim, J. Her, G.-H. Yang, D. Lee, Odar: Aerial manipulation platform enabling omnidirectional wrench generation, *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 23 (4) (2018) 1907–1918. doi:10.1109/TMECH.2018.2848255.
- [11] A. Praveen, X. Ma, H. Manoj, V. L. Venkatesh, M. Rastgaar, R. M. Voyles, Inspection-on-the-fly using hybrid physical interaction control for aerial manipulators, in: *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2020, pp. 1583–1588. doi:10.1109/IROS45743.2020.9341397.
- [12] K. Bodie, M. Brunner, M. Pantic, S. Walser, P. Pfändler, U. Angst, R. Siegwart, J. Nieto, Active interaction force control for contact-based inspection with a fully actuated aerial vehicle, *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 37 (3) (2021) 709–722. doi:10.1109/TRO.2020.3036623.
- [13] M. Tognon, H. A. T. Chávez, E. Gasparin, Q. Sablé, D. Bicego, A. Mallet, M. Lany, G. Santi, B. Revaz, J. Cortés, A. Franchi, A truly-redundant aerial manipulator system with application to push-and-slide inspection in industrial plants, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 4 (2) (2019) 1846–1851. doi:10.1109/LRA.2019.2895880.
- [14] R. Rashad, D. Bicego, R. Jiao, S. Sanchez-Escalonilla, S. Stramigioli, Towards vision-based impedance control for the contact inspection of unknown generically-shaped surfaces with a fully-actuated uav, in: *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2020, pp. 1605–1612. doi:10.1109/IROS45743.2020.9341203.
- [15] P. J. Sanchez-Cuevas, A. Gonzalez-Morgado, N. Cortes, D. B. Gayango, A. E. Jimenez-Cano, A. Ollero, G. Heredia, Fully-actuated aerial manipulator for infrastructure contact inspection: Design, modeling, localization, and control, *Sensors* 20 (17) (2020). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/17/4708>

- [16] M. Ryll, D. Bicego, M. Giurato, M. Lovera, A. Franchi, Fast-hex – a morphing hexarotor: Design, mechanical implementation, control and experimental validation, *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* (2021) 1–1 doi: 10.1109/TMECH.2021.3099197.
- [17] S. Rajappa, M. Ryll, H. H. Bühlhoff, A. Franchi, Modeling, control and design optimization for a fully-actuated hexarotor aerial vehicle with tilted propellers, in: *2015 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2015, pp. 4006–4013. doi:10.1109/ICRA.2015.7139759.
- [18] C. Li, C. Xue, Y. Bai, Experimental investigation on aerodynamics of nonplanar rotor pairs in a multi-rotor uav, in: *2019 14th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications (ICIEA)*, 2019, pp. 911–915. doi:10.1109/ICIEA.2019.8834124.
- [19] P. Abbaraju, X. Ma, G. Jiang, M. Rastgaar, R. M. Voyles, Aerodynamic modeling of fully-actuated multirotor uavs with nonparallel actuators, in: *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2021, pp. 9639–9645. doi:10.1109/IROS51168.2021.9636572.
- [20] S. Wang, L. Ma, B. Li, K. Zhang, Architecture design and flight control of a novel octopus shaped multirotor vehicle, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 7 (1) (2022) 311–317. doi:10.1109/LRA.2021.3124077.
- [21] G. Jiang, R. Voyles, K. Sebesta, H. Greiner, Estimation and optimization of fully-actuated multirotor platform with nonparallel actuation mechanism, in: *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2017, pp. 6843–6848. doi:10.1109/IROS.2017.8206605.
- [22] C. Pose, J. Giribet, I. Mas, Fault tolerance analysis of a hexarotor with reconfigurable tilted rotors, in: *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2020, pp. 9359–9365. doi:10.1109/ICRA40945.2020.9196552.
- [23] R. Ji, J. Ma, S. Sam Ge, Modeling and control of a tilting quadcopter, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems* 56 (4) (2020) 2823–2834. doi:10.1109/TAES.2019.2955525.
- [24] G. Flores, A. M. de Oca, A. Flores, Robust nonlinear control for the fully actuated hexa-rotor: Theory and experiments, *IEEE Control Systems Letters* 7 (2023) 277–282. doi:10.1109/LCSYS.2022.3188517.
- [25] G. Throneberry, C. Hocut, A. Abdelkefi, Multi-rotor wake propagation and flow development modeling: A review, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* 127 (2021) 100762. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2021.100762.
- [26] A. Matus-Vargas, G. Gamez, J. Martinez-Carranza, Ground effect on rotorcraft unmanned aerial vehicles: a review, *Intelligent Service Robotics* 14 (2021) 1–20. doi:10.1007/s11370-020-00344-5.
- [27] Y. H. Hsiao, P. Chirarattananon, Ceiling effects for hybrid aerial-surface locomotion of small rotorcraft, *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 24 (5) (2019) 2316–2327. doi:10.1109/TMECH.2019.2929589.
- [28] T. Nishio, M. Zhao, F. Shi, T. Anzai, K. Kawaharazuka, K. Okada, M. Inaba, Stable control in climbing and descending flight under upper walls using ceiling effect model based on aerodynamics, in: *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2020, pp. 172–178. doi:10.1109/ICRA40945.2020.9197137.
- [29] B. B. Kocer, M. E. Tiryaki, M. Pratama, T. Tjahjowidodo, G. G. L. Seet, Aerial robot control in close proximity to ceiling: A force estimation-based nonlinear mpc, in: *2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, IEEE, 2019, pp. 2813–2819.
- [30] S. A. Conyers, M. J. Rutherford, K. P. Valavanis, An empirical evaluation of ceiling effect for small-scale rotorcraft, in: *2018 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, 2018, pp. 243–249. doi:10.1109/ICUAS.2018.8453469.
- [31] C. Powers, D. Mellinger, A. Kushleyev, B. Kothmann, V. Kumar, *Influence of Aerodynamics and Proximity Effects in Quadrotor Flight*, Springer International Publishing, 2013, pp. 289–302. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-00065-7_21.
- [32] B. B. Kocer, T. Tjahjowidodo, G. G. L. Seet, Centralized predictive ceiling interaction control of quadrotor vtol uav, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 76 (2018) 455–465. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2018.02.020.
- [33] P. Sanchez-Cuevas, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Multirotor aerodynamic effects in aerial manipulation, in: *Aerial Robotic Manipulation*, Springer, 2019, pp. 67–82.

- [34] V. Britcher, S. Bergbreiter, Use of a mems differential pressure sensor to detect ground, ceiling, and walls on small quadrotors, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 6 (3) (2021) 4568–4575. doi:10.1109/LRA.2021.3068661.
- 535 [35] D. C. Robinson, H. Chung, K. Ryan, Computational investigation of micro rotorcraft near-wall hovering aerodynamics, in: 2014 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS), 2014, pp. 1055–1063. doi:10.1109/ICUAS.2014.6842357.
- [36] C. Ding, L. Lu, A tilting-rotor unmanned aerial vehicle for enhanced aerial locomotion and manipulation capabilities: Design, control, and applications, *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 26 (4) (2021) 2237–2248. doi:10.1109/TMECH.2020.3036346.
- 540 [37] A. Garofano-Soldado, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Aerodynamic interference in confined environments with tilted propellers: Wall effect and corner effect, in: 2021 Aerial Robotic Systems Physically Interacting with the Environment (AIRPHARO), 2021, pp. 1–8. doi:10.1109/AIRPHARO52252.2021.9571031.
- [38] Y.-H. Hsiao, S. Bai, Y. Zhou, H. Jia, R. Ding, Y. Chen, Z. Wang, P. Chirarattananon, Energy efficient perching and takeoff of a miniature rotorcraft, *Communications Engineering* 2 (2023). doi:10.1038/s44172-023-00087-y.
- 545 [39] R. W. Deters, G. K. A. Krishnan, M. S. Selig, Reynolds number effects on the performance of small-scale propellers, in: 32nd AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference, 2014. doi:10.2514/6.2014-2151.
- [40] B. B. Kocer, V. Kumtepli, T. Tjahjowidodo, M. Pratama, A. Tripathi, G. S. G. Lee, Y. Wang, Uav control in close proximities-ceiling effect on battery lifetime, in: 2019 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Autonomous Systems (ICoIAS), IEEE, pp. 193–197.
- 550 [41] X. He, G. Kou, M. Calaf, K. Leang, In-ground-effect modeling and nonlinear disturbance observer for multi-rotor uav control, *Journal of Dynamic Systems, Measurement, and Control* 141 (03 2019). doi:10.1115/1.4043221.
- [42] H. Keshavarzian, K. Daneshjou, Modified under-actuated quadrotor model for forwarding flight in the presence of ground effect, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 89 (2019) 242–252. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2019.04.001.
- 555 [43] P. Sanchez-Cuevas, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Characterization of the aerodynamic ground effect and its influence in multirotor control, *International Journal of Aerospace Engineering* (2017). doi:10.1155/2017/1823056.
- [44] S. A. Conyers, M. J. Rutherford, K. P. Valavanis, An empirical evaluation of ground effect for small-scale rotorcraft, in: 2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2018, pp. 1244–1250. doi:10.1109/ICRA.2018.8461035.
- 560 [45] V. Lakshminarayan, T. Kalra, J. Baeder, Detailed computational investigation of a hovering microscale rotor in ground effect, *AIAA Journal* 51 (2013) 893–909. doi:10.2514/1.J051789.
- [46] X. Kan, J. Thomas, H. Teng, H. G. Tanner, V. Kumar, K. Karydis, Analysis of ground effect for small-scale uavs in forward flight, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 4 (4) (2019) 3860–3867. doi:10.1109/LRA.2019.2929993.
- 565 [47] I. Cheeseman, W. Bennett, The effect of ground on a helicopter rotor in forward flight, *ARC R and M* 3021 (1955).
- [48] E. Fradenburgh, The helicopter and the ground effect machine,, *Journal of the American Helicopter Society* 5 (4) (1960) 26–28.
- [49] S. F. R.L Marr, D.G Ford, Analysis of the wind tunnel test of a tilt rotor power force model, Technical report NASA-CR-137529, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Moffett Field, CA, USA, June (1974).
- 570 [50] H. Xin, J. Prasad, D. Peters, N. Itoga, N. Iboshi, T. Nagashima, Ground effect aerodynamics of lifting rotors hovering above inclined ground plane, in: 17th Applied Aerodynamics Conference, 1999. doi:10.2514/6.1999-3223.
- [51] S. Platzer, J. Rauleder, Investigation on hovering rotors over inclined ground planes - a computational and experimental study, in: 44th Eur. Rotorcr. Forum 2018, ERF 2018, vol. 1, no. September, 2018.
- 575 [52] C. Pasquali, J. Serafini, G. Bernardini, J. Milluzzo, M. Gennaretti, Numerical-experimental correlation of hovering rotor aerodynamics in ground effect, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 106 (2020) 106079. doi:10.1016/j.ast.2020.106079.

- [53] J. I. Milluzzo, A. Martinez, S. Drayton, S. Davids, Experimental investigation of rotors hovering above inclined surfaces, *J. Am. Helicopter Soc.* 66 (2) (2021). doi:10.4050/jahs.66.022005.
- [54] E. Davis, P. E. I. Pounds, Passive position control of a quadrotor with ground effect interaction, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 1 (1) (2016) 539–545. doi:10.1109/LRA.2016.2514351.
- [55] A. Garofano-Soldado, P. J. Sanchez-Cuevas, G. Heredia, A. Ollero, Numerical-experimental evaluation and modelling of aerodynamic ground effect for small-scale tilted propellers at low reynolds numbers, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 126 (2022) 107625. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2022.107625.
- [56] H. Dekker, D. Ragni, W. Baars, F. Scarano, M. Tuinstra, Aerodynamic interactions of side-by-side rotors in ground proximity, *AIAA Journal* 60 (2022) 1–11. doi:10.2514/1.J061105.
- [57] P. A. Silva, P. Tsoutsanis, A. F. Antoniadis, Simple multiple reference frame for high-order solution of hovering rotors with and without ground effect, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 111 (2021) 106518. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2021.106518.
- [58] C. Paz, E. Suarez, C. Gil, C. Baker, Cfd analysis of the aerodynamic effects on the stability of the flight of a quadcopter uav in the proximity of walls and ground, *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 206 (2020) 104378. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2020.104378.
- [59] E. Loureiro, N. Oliveira, P. Hallak, F. Bastos, L. Rocha, R. Delmonte, A. Lemonge, Evaluation of low fidelity and cfd methods for the aerodynamic performance of a small propeller, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 108 (2021) 106402. doi:10.1016/j.ast.2020.106402.
- [60] M. Rostami, A. hamzeh Farajollahi, Aerodynamic performance of mutual interaction tandem propellers with ducted uav, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 108 (2021) 106399. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2020.106399.
- [61] X. Wang, Y. Liu, C. Huang, Research on finite ground effect of a rotor, in: 2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2019, pp. 6935–6940. doi:10.1109/IR0S40897.2019.8968083.
- [62] M. Merchant, L. Miller, Propeller performance measurement for low reynolds number uav applications, 2006. doi:10.2514/6.2006-1127.
- [63] A. Garofano-Soldado, Supplementary material of aerodynamic interactions of non-planar rotor pairs and model derivation in ground approach (2023).
URL <https://github.com/AmbarGarofano-Soldado/Ground-effect-results>
- [64] C. Paz, E. Suarez, C. Gil, J. Vence, Assessment of the methodology for the cfd simulation of the flight of a quadcopter uav, *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 218 (2021) 104776.
- [65] H. A. Kutty, P. Rajendran, 3d cfd simulation and experimental validation of small apc slow flyer propeller blade, *Aerospace* 4 (1) (2017). doi:10.3390/aerospace4010010.
- [66] A. I. (2015), Ansys fluent theory guide.
- [67] F. Menter, Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications, *AIAA Journal* 32 (8) (1994) 1598–1605. doi:10.2514/3.12149.
- [68] M. Cerny, C. Breitsamter, Investigation of small-scale propellers under non-axial inflow conditions, *Aerospace Science and Technology* 106 (2020) 106048. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2020.106048.
- [69] T.-M. Propellers, T-motor store official.
URL <https://store.tmotor.com/>
- [70] R. W. Prouty, Helicopter performance, stability, and control, 1986.
- [71] R. T. N. Chen, A survey of nonuniform inflow models for rotorcraft flight dynamics and control applications, NASA TM-102219 (1990).
- [72] K. Singh, M. Mehndiratta, M. Feroskhan, Quadplus: Design, modeling, and receding-horizon-based control of a hyperdynamic quadrotor, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems* 58 (3) (2022) 1766–1779. doi:10.1109/TAES.2021.3133314.